

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING ATOMIC PHYSICS COMPUTER MODELING USING THE MATHEMATICA SYSTEM

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Attention to education in our country is growing day by day. In order to further develop the education system and provide education on an equal basis with developed countries, the higher education system in our country is gradually switching to training using a credit-modular system.

Atomic physics are special disciplines for students of physical specialties in the higher education system. Computer technology is important in explaining their satisfaction. It also has the ability to solve equations, draw graphs, create models and much more using the Mathematica package[1,2,3].

Looking at world experience, scientific work has been carried out on the use of computer technology in teaching atomic physics to demonstrate patterns, obtain results in laboratory work, consolidate topics, and conduct intermediate and final control. In their work, the method of demonstrating patterns corresponds to our scientific work.

In higher educational institutions (Karakalpak State University named after Berdak), the optics course in the IV semester is a lecture of 60 hours and practical classes of 30 hours.

Now let's start modeling light on a two-dimensional diffraction grating, x-rays and electron beams in crystalline solids based on a single computer simulation. We use the Mathematica computer algebra system, which we constantly used in our previous works [4-5].

Apparently the question "What is a hydrogen spectrum and how does it reveal information about the atomic structure of hydrogen?" is one of the attractive questions associated with the teaching of both optics and atomic physics and quantum mechanics. The question posed is clear, concise, and focused on a key aspect of the topic - the relationship between the hydrogen spectrum and atomic structure.

Typically, a lecture on the spectrum of hydrogen atoms can be read in the following order: an explanation of the concept of spectra and how to obtain them, a brief history of the discovery of the visible spectrum of hydrogen, the emission and absorption spectra of hydrogen and their characteristic features,

an explanation of the hydrogen spectrum based on the Bohr model, the relationship between the spectrum hydrogen and the structure of hydrogen. Naturally, the lecture ends with a conclusion and a summary of its key points. This order ensures a logical and comprehensive development of the topic, starting with a basic understanding of the hydrogen atom and ending with the more complex topic of quantum mechanical explanation.

At the same time, computer modeling of the spectrum of hydrogen atoms is a useful tool for understanding and predicting the behavior of hydrogen spectra. There are key points to note regarding computer simulation:

1. Accurate modeling: Computer modeling can accurately model the spectrum of hydrogen and predict the behavior of its spectral lines, taking into account quantized energy levels and transitions.
2. Testing Theories: Computer simulations can be used to test theories and hypotheses about the hydrogen spectrum, providing valuable insight into the underlying physics.
3. Experimental Verification: Computer simulations can be compared with experimental results to check their accuracy and identify any inconsistencies.
4. Visualization: Computer modeling can provide a visual representation of the hydrogen spectrum, making it easier to understand and interpret.

Overall, computer modeling of the hydrogen spectrum is a powerful tool for gaining a deeper understanding of the behavior of the hydrogen atom and its spectral lines.

A pedagogical experiment was conducted to study the influence of a computer demonstration on the assimilation of the studied phenomenon by 2-3 year students of the physics specialty using the Wolfram Mathematica system, which is especially well suited for modeling the spectrum of hydrogen atoms due to the presence of an extensive library of mathematical functions and the ability to perform complex calculations [1-3]. Below we discuss the use of Wolfram Mathematica to model the spectrum of hydrogen atoms and demonstrate how this tool can be used to accurately predict the behavior of these spectral lines.

The starting expression for conducting a computer demonstration is the Rydberg formula $\frac{1}{\lambda} = R \left(\frac{1}{k^2} - \frac{1}{n^2} \right)$, where $R = 0,0109737 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. For different series, the value of k has different integer values.

Using the Rydberg formula, you can obtain the wavelengths of all spectral series.

Wherein $Table\left[\left(R \left(\frac{1}{k^2} - \frac{1}{n^2} \right)\right)^{-1}, \{n, k + 1, 15\}\right]$ gives all the wavelengths for the series corresponding to the number k . $R = 0,0109737 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ - Rydberg constant.

For example, for the Balmer series ($k=2$) the following values for wavelengths (in nanometers) are obtained: 656.112; 486.009; 433.937; 410.070, etc. To visualize the received data, use the command:

$$ListLinePlot \left[Table \left[\left\{ \left\{ \left(R \left(\frac{1}{k^2} - \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \right)^{-1}, 0 \right\}, \left\{ \left(R \left(\frac{1}{k^2} - \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \right)^{-1}, 10 \right\} \right\}, \{n, k\} + 1, 13 \right] \right]$$

Here, according to this command, the value of the quantum number n changes from $k+1$ to 13. The number 10 written on the second curly bracket corresponds to the length of the resulting line along the vertical axis. The thickness of the resulting lines can be changed using the option `PlotStyle` $\rightarrow$ `AbsoluteThickness[ $q$ ]`, where q denotes the thickness of the lines. Calculations performed using the `ListLinePlot` command give the picture shown in Fig. 1.

Drawing. 1. Arrangement of spectral lines of the Balmer series, plotted by Wolfram

Mathematica:

1. Н.А.Вавилов, В.Г.Халин, А.В.Юрков. Mathematica для не математика. Электронное издание. Москва. МЦНМО. 2021. 483 с.
2. Stephen Wolfram. An Elementary Introduction to the Wolfram Language. Second Edition. Champaign, IL, USA : Wolfram Media, Inc. 2017. 339 p.
3. Gerd Baumann. Mathematica for theoretical physics. 1. Classical Mechanics and Nonlinear Dynamics Second Edition. Springer. 2005. 544 p.
4. Б.Абдикамалов, Г.Бабахова . Компьютерное моделирование спектра водородоподобных атомов при помощи системы Mathematica СПО 7(335) 2023. 27-29стр.
5. G.Z. Babakhova Computer simulation of demonstration experiments on the diffraction of light, X-rays and electrons for undergraduate and graduate students in physics//Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities ISSN 2749-0866 Vol.2 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences <http://berlinstudies.de/> 974-979 p